

Work-life Balance and Employee Performance of 7-up Bottling Company, Plc., Ninth Mile Corner, Enugu

Authored by

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Abstract

The study was on work-life balance and employee performance of 7-up Bottling Company Plc. Ninth Mile Comer Enugu. It was set to evaluate the influence of flexible time on employee output, examine the effect of telework on employee efficiency, and assess the effect of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Comer, Enugu. Three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study while a questionnaire was used as an instrument. The study population size was 800. Through Taro Yamane formula, a sample size of 267 emerged. The data obtained were presented using frequency tables and analysed in percentages. Chi-square was used for testing the hypotheses. The study revealed that there was a significant positive influence of flexible time on employee output, there was a significant positive effect of telework on employee efficiency and there a was significant positive effect of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner, Enugu, It was concluded that work-life balance had significant positive effect on employee performance of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Comer, Enugu. The study recommended that the management of the 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner, Enugu, should focus more on different work-life balance incentives, such as compressed work schedules, wellness programmes and telecommuting to enhance workers' performance. Management of the firm should make provision for nursing mothers in terms of child care assistance in form of crèche and after school services; and management should ensure job sharing (shift work) for employees on essential duties to reduce the stress and also for them to have time for their respective families.

Keywords: Work-life Balance; Employee Performance; 7-up Bottling Company; Ninth Mile Corner

Introduction

Today, work-life balance has become a prevalent concern to both employers and employees of most organizations. Most recently, there has been an increase in the thought about the significance that work has on the family as well as life of employees (Abioro, 2018). Thus, the situation has stimulated many studies on the work-life of individuals in the workplace. Especially, in today's global business environment, where there is a blur between work roles and personal roles. Work is no longer restricted to the office space due to advancements in technology led a with high level of competition originating largely from efforts to deliver excellent service, thus the encumbrance of work on employee personal life is usually enormous (Anderson, Coffey, Byerly, 2018). Therefore, achieving work-life balance in this era of fast pace globalization and competitiveness as well as creating a balance between professional and personal life is a challenge for most individuals in the workplace (Goldstein, 2015). Work-life balance is a crucial issue for every employee in government and a private institution today. This is because there will be a decrease in employee productivity if an organization does not think about the work balance of employees properly and is not managed properly (Abioro, 2018). Work balance programme began in 1980 when company policies and regulations allow employees to work effectively and efficiently and provide flexible time to deal with the personal problems of these employees. The fact is, that the workforce places more emphasis on work-life balance rather than on income alone.

Work-life balance includes a balance between work and personal life that both bring satisfaction to the individual (Edwards, Rothbard, 2019). The dilemma for employees that occurs today is that when they compete for work demands, there is an abundance of negative effects on the work-life balance of employees ranging from increased stress, work fatigue, disruption of family and work relationships Awan and Taufique (2017). Balancing the demands of employee work and family life is very difficult. This can trigger stress or decrease employee productivity and welfare In this case, the work-life balance must be considered to allocate available resources such as time, thought and work wisely among the personal lives of the employees themselves.

This also must be a concern of the organisation regarding how important the work-life balance is for its employees. Work-life balance is how to create a supportive work environment, enabling job balance and personal responsibility because this will strengthen employee loyalty and productivity (Meenakshi *et al.*, 2013). Many organizations in western countries recognize the importance of work-life balance, where employees now prefer work-life balance over higher wages. Work-life balance contains three components, such as a balanced time, a balance of work and family involvement, and fair (Kossek, Li,rio and Valcour, 2013). It is time we no longer talk about a tight work bureaucracy, but relaxed and flexible work because managing balanced work life and personal life is important for employees. Companies must realize the importance of work-life balance consistently concerning productivity, employee performance, and improving the quality of life of employees (Allen, 2019).

Work-life balance policies are key factors for the success of an organization that depends on its employees for the achievement of organizational goals. Kossek, Li,rio and Valcour (2013) define work-life balance as "satisfaction and perceptions of success in meeting work and non-work role demands, low levels of conflict among roles and opportunity for inter-role enrichment." The concept in this context is not restricted to prioritizing work and personal life roles of employees but also includes how it affects employees' psychological, economic and mental wellbeing.

Moreover, employees play a key role in any business formation and therefore there is need to provide an enabling environment at all levels so as to attain the stated objectives and goals of the organization. However, demand between work and home is becoming a major concern for employees in recent years. Some of this anxiety has to do with the demographic and workplace changes, especially for women in the labor force that are required to do longer working hours (Azeem & Akhtar, 2014). In reaction to these alterations alongside the dispute they produce between the numerous roles that individual hold, various establishments are gradually pressured to come up with work practices arrangement that will facilitate employee's efforts to accomplish both their work-related and their private errands (Ataullah and Sahota, 2016). Work-life balance is a critical issue which is of paramount worry to every employee at different level be it public or private segment alike. The issue is far more than prioritizing the work role and one's personal life. It equally has a way of influencing one's psychological, social, and economic and ultimately the mental well-being of an individual. Nevertheless, the above assertion will reflect in the output of the employees,

which invariably affects or her their productivity at the workplace in the long run if not properly managed (Allen, 2019).

Fundamentally, work-life balance practices are an essential part of human resource management which is getting collective and adequate consideration from government, employers of labour and researchers. Reason being that, it is a solid component of motivation for improved organizational responsiveness concerning the application and administration of balance of work-life strategies (Ugwu and Orga, 2006). It is also mostly connected with stability in between the quality of time and energy an individual dedicates to work and private undertakings to sustain a harmonious life. The practices of work life work-life approaches are to enhance stability between the hassles of the occupation and the robust management of life outside work station and flexible work environment.

Despite scholars' and researchers' efforts in the management field to look into the frequent challenges being faced by worker's job and their personal life, employees still experience conflict as regard the individual life as they continue to look for the kind of life they desired. Hence, harmonizing work and family life poses as a major challenge facing employees in the organizations. It is against this backdrop that the study investigated work – life balance and employee performance of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner, Enugu.

Statement of the Problem

In the Nigerian context, the encumbrance of work roles on employee family roles is further heightened by demographic changes, an increase in the number of women in the workforce, dual-career couples, a rise in the number of single parents, and employees' growing reluctance to accept long hours of work culture. Employees prioritize work and non-work roles which results in work-family imbalance.

There is an increased level of stress in employees, a rising rate of drug abuse, decreased productivity creased rate of turnover and absenteeism, decreased level of job satisfaction, etc. which influence employee performance. Also, high attrition rates and increasing demand for work-life balance have forced organizations to look beyond run off -of-the-mill mill human resource interventions. Additionally, there are systemic barriers that hinder the implementation work-life life balance policies, such as leadership failure which has birthed political, economic and social challenges that are the primary source work-life life conflict, they include corruption, weak institutions can notify to monitor and enforce employment standards, high unemployment ratios, poverty, inflation and a plethora of others. Other barriers that are more directly hindering the successful implementation of work life-balance policies in an organization to include role overload, long hours of work culture, lack of supportive organizational culture, reluctance to accept available work-life policies, a wide gap between Work life-balance practices and employees' understanding of the implementation of these policies, etc. With all these challenges at play, it is evident that even though there are available Work life-balance policies in organizations, successful implementation has been very poor, there is, therefore, a need for scholars to research ways in which organizations can assist employees to achieve Work life-balance in order to improve on their performance.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to investigate work-life and employee productivity in 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner, Enugu. Other specific objectives were to:

- i. Evaluate the influence of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner, Enugu.
- ii. Examine the effect of telework on employee efficiency of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner, Enugu.
- iii. Assess the effect of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner, Enugu.

Research Questions

- i. What is the influence of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu?
- ii. What is the effect of telework on employee efficiency of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu?
- iii. What is the effect of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated to guide the study;

- i. There is positive influence of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.
- ii. There is a positive effect of telework on employee efficiency of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.
- iii. There is significant positive impact of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on work-life balance and employee productivity of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. The study was done in Enugu State Nigeria in the year 2021. More so, the study evaluated the impact of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company Plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. In addition, it investigated the effect of telework on employee efficiency in 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. Moreover, it assessed the impact of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Work-life life balance

For organizations to succeed and perform there is need to address the needs of these valuable assets, hence the need to address aspects such as work-life balance and other factors which affect employees' productivity. Atallah and Sahota (2016) refer to Work-Life balance as the level to which an employee experiences feeling fulfilled and having their needs met in both work and non-work aspects of life. Through experiencing greater work-life balance individuals detail feeling better in general (1or example greater job and personal life fulfillment) and tend to behave in good ways (for example lower turnover and absenteeism). Organisations, therefore, need to adopt a strategy for improving employees' Work-Life Balance (WLB) to satisfy both the organizational objectives and employee needs. This means that every organization would be interested in bringing about a superior level of productivity from employees. To resolve Work-Life imbalance happening among today's professional there are two major issues that need to be understood: Role overload (RO) meaning having too much to do and too little time to do it in limited time frame and Role interference (RI) meaning when incompatible demands make it difficult, if not impossible, for employees to perform all their roles well. Asserts that role interference in turn consists of two factors; that is work to family interference (WTF), where work interferes with family life and family to work interference (FTW) where family demands such as child and elder care affect work. However, achieving work-life balance may be the main concern and desire of an individual employee: but it is not his or her sole responsibility to be a lone fighter. Employers being the norms and conditions setters at workplace are considered to be facilitators of work-life balance.

Formal work-life balance strategies are:

1. **Work-life stress management**
Stress management services and programmes are provided by an external company specializing in this type of support, information and counseling service. These services should be confidential and can be offered to either individuals or groups of employees. The benefits of this programme can include decreased absenteeism, accidents and stress related disability. It can lead to increased employee productivity and prevention of problems, which could negatively impact the employee's work and home life.
2. **Workplace Flexibility**
Flextime is an arrangement whereby employees can vary the scheduling of their working hours within specified guidelines. Essentially, it allows employees, on an individual or collective basis, to determine the start and end times of their working day. Flextime allows the employees to plan their workday around their personal lives. This practice can reduce the tardiness and absenteeism, increases in employee morale and employee job satisfaction and ultimately employee performance.
3. **Tele working**
Tele work, also referred to as telecommuting, is an arrangement whereby an employee, at least on a periodic basis, fulfills his or her regularly scheduled job responsibilities at a remote place. (Own residence) telework can be an advantage for employees as they can organize their workday around their personal and family needs. It can also decrease the transport expenses and reduce commuting time. Tele work allows the employee to work in a less stressful and disruptive environment.
4. **Workplace child care**
Employees may have their children looked after at or near the workplace. The child care center may be owned by the company or be managed by a board of directors that includes representatives of the company and parents whose children go to the center. This facilitates the employees to easier access to a child care service and help to reduce the stress experienced by the parents.
5. **Health and safety promotion**
A healthy workplace provides mutual benefits for employers and employees within a common belief that good health practices by both will lead to individual and organizational self- fulfillment and productivity. Health promotion is the process of enabling employees to increase control over and to improve their physical, emotional and social health. This programme enables all the employees to improve health and maintain their good health. Therefore, the types of health activities can have positive impact on physical, emotional, and social environment.
6. **Job Sharing:**
This is an agreement that allows two or more individual to engage in a full time work, whereby they shared the responsibilities between themselves. (Hayman, 2010). Work life balance practices is therefore a thoughtful organizational modifications in strategies or administrative philosophy which are planned to lessen work-life conflict and support employees to be more active both at work and in other sphere of life.
7. **Work Leave Initiatives**
Leave is the number of days or hours an organization permits an employee to be away from work within a period of time without consequences. Haar, Russo, Sune, & Ollier-Malaterre, (2019) insist leave initiatives are best applied at the beginning of each calendar year so as not to interrupt the smooth running of the organization as well as avoid conflicting situations. Leave programmes cut across various individuals and aspects in the workplace, it includes annual vacation, parental leave, casual leave, medical leave, compassionate leave, study leave, career leave etc. In Nigeria, Section 18 of the Labour Act, 1990 provides that upon completing a qualifying period of service of 12 months continuous service, employees are entitled to annual leave with pay for the purpose of rest and/or recreation and every organisation is compelled to implement this policy as noncompliance will be tantamount to disobedience to the rule of law in the country.

Effectiveness

In general, effectiveness is referred to as the degree to which set objectives are accomplished and policies achieve what they were designed to achieve. It focuses on affecting the purpose that is achieving the required or projected results. A program or service is said to be effective if such a program is able to accomplish set objectives or estimated outcomes. As regards workers, it is a measure of how well workers productivity levels meet set goals and objectives of the organization (Yesufu, 2000). Therefore an employee is said to be effective when he/she is able to achieve desired results in line with organizational goals and objectives

Efficiency

Efficiency on the other hand is productivity of estimated effects; specifically, productivity without any form of waste. This has to do with workers abilities to work productively with minimum waste in terms of energy, time and cost. Efficiency is more or less a contrast between the use of inputs in a clearly defined process and generated outputs. For instance, given a specified number of input or resources, a decision-making entity be it individual, corporate, administrative institution, or a state realizes a level of output considered to be the maximum achievable based on the present conditions, then such an entity is assumed to be efficient. However, if it generates lesser than what it is estimated to generate it is said to be inefficient. As such efficiency stems from the correlation between inputs and outputs, and is referred to basically as the degree to which outputs are produced while minimizing manufacturing costs (Harris, 2001).

Productivity

Awan and Taufique (2017) define productivity as "how much and how good we produce from the resources used," whereas The European Association of National Productivity Centres (EANPC, 2005) defines productivity as "how efficiently and effectively products and services are being produced." Measuring productivity can help firms to follow the missions, vision, policies, objectives and targets (Dealey, 2017; Dreher, 2018; Grzywacz & Carlson, 2017). Likewise, enabling firms identify their weakness and strengths along with opportunities and threats which evolving from market. In view of this, some researchers believe that the profit report of the company is not enough and it is only the last result, while the productivity report determines either efficiency or effectiveness of process and policies.

When the factors affecting the productivity are managed properly the situation becomes favorable. The resulting effects productivity may include improved working conditions, introduction of needed technology, training of employees, motivation, better leadership, favorable rules, regulations, policies and career development opportunities which will in turn influence performance standards positively thereby resulting in higher customer satisfaction levels, which is good for business.

Employee Productivity

Employee productivity can be thought of as how effectively organizations and the people working in them produce value from available inputs, Goldstein (2015). Guthrie (2016), assure that employee Productivity also known as labour productivity is known as the output per person or system. Burke, and Greenglass (2019). define productivity as the ratio of outputs to inputs. It refers to the volume of output produced from a given volume of inputs or resources. If the firm becomes more productive, then it has become more efficient, since productivity is an efficiency measure. Productivity in itself has so many benefits to the organization, Helmlle, Botero, and Seibold (2014) believe that it translates to real income and that means that the firm can meet its duties to customers, suppliers, employees, shareholders and government (taxes and regulation) and still remain competitive or improve its competitiveness in the market place. Productivity is not different as seen in different perspectives and high productivity levels translate into lower unit costs and it is one of the drivers of success in the organization. Productivity, therefore is growing the business in a way where the employees and the employer are satisfied.

Theoretical Review

The following theories will serve as the theoretical basis for this study:

Work-family Border Theory

Work-family border theory is devoted only to work and family domains. The outcome of interest in this theory is the work-family balance, which refers to "contentment and good operation at work and home, with a depth of role clash" (Clark, 2000). Central to this theory is the idea that "work and family" constitute different domains or spheres which influence each other. Given their opposite purposes and cultures, work and home can be likened to two different countries where are differences in language or word use, differences in what constitutes acceptable behaviour, and differences in how to achieve tasks. For the working theory of this study, we will situate this research on the work-family border theory.

For the study, Boundary and Border theory and Spillover theory served as the theoretical underpinning upon which this study is anchored. A study by Orga, Mbah and Ekechukwu, (2018) emphasizes that both family and work are not isolated domains but are symbiotic spheres or parts with penetrable boundaries. The Boarder theory has to do with domestic and work spheres. It lays emphasis on the fact that individuals are everyday boarder crosser as they progressed between work and home. Clark (2000) in his study postulated that the aim of border theory is all about aiding performance and functioning at home and at work, with a lowest of role dispute.

Spillover Theory

Spillover theory which was postulated by Guest (2002) opines that the circumstances wherein spillover can occur between the family (macro system) and the work (micro system). Spillover may be negative or positive as the case may be. If work-family connections are strictly designed in space and time, at that moment, spillover in terms of energy, behaviour and time will be negative. Also, when there is the flexibility that all individuals to participate and the join family together with work duties, this will bring about positive spillover that is contributory to realizing a fit a work-life balance. Spillover therefore happens, when there is intrusion of one phase of life into another. The significance of these theories to the study is that management is expected to embrace work-life balance practices which will make even employee to be more committed to attaining higher productivity levels

Empirical Review

Several studies have been carried out that are related to work-life balance. Anderson, Coffey, and Byerly (2018) investigated the empirical analysis of flexible time and its impact on employee's output. The research aimed to analyze the relationship between work life balance policies and employee job satisfaction. Questionnaire was filled by 240 respondents who were used for the survey. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the quantitative data using correlation. The findings of this study emphasized that each of the work life balance policies on its own is a predictor of productivity.

Azeem and Akhtar (2014) investigated the influence of telework on employee efficiency. This was aimed at exploring the influence of work life balance and job satisfaction has on organization commitment among healthcare employee. Questionnaire was distributed to 275 respondents in the healthcare sector. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the quantitative data including correlation and reliabilities. The finding of the empirical test shows that employee in the health care sector have a moderate level of perceived work life balance, job satisfaction and commitment.

Akanji, Mordi, and Ojo (2015) investigated the impact of shift work on employee effectiveness. The types of Work Life Balance initiatives available in the three sectors were explored and the barriers to implementation of the Work Life Balance initiatives were identified. Quantitative method was used. This was achieved using an in-depth case study analysis of these sectors. The data set comprised of responses from both managers and employees in the Banking sector

with five hundred and eighty six copies of the questionnaire retrieved. The Educational sector comprised of both managers and employees with five hundred and thirty one copies of the questionnaire retrieved; while five hundred and seven copies retrieved from the Power Sector. The findings reveal that there is diversity in terms of how respondents perceive the concept of Work-Life Balance. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the quantitative data including Anova There is a wide gap between corporate Work Life Balance practices and employees' understanding of the concept; the paper suggests some policy implications which would aid the implementation of Work Life Balance policies in the studied sectors.

Harris (2014) investigated on the exploration of the effect of work life balance on productivity. The aim of the study was to explore the connection between work life balance and organization productivity and whether work life balance practice possibly decreases employee turnover and absenteeism. 200 respondents in the banking industry were used for the survey. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data. Chi square was used to analyze the data. The finding of the result was that there is a positive relationship between work life balance practice and employee turnover. It also found out that management support was not satisfactory.

Hon and Chon (2015) investigated the impact of work-life balance on employee performance. The study aimed to analyze the relationship between work lifework-life and employee performance. 96 employees were used for the survey and questionnaire was distributed to them in which the data was used to run an analysis. Pearson moment correlation was used to analyze the data. The finding of the result was that there is a positive relationship between work-life balance and employee performance. Also, there was a need for systematic effort to enhance work-life balance of the employee to achieve better employee performance.

Beauregard (2016) investigated work life balance practices and policies manager and employee experience in Nigeria banking sector. The aim of the research is to explore the extent to which work life balance policies/practices in organization in Nigeria. Questionnaire was used as the instrument and 600 respondents were used for the survey. Spearman's correlation analysis was used to analyze the data. The finding of the empirical study shows that there is need to enlighten employee about the various work life balance.

Gap in Empirical Review

Studies on work - life balance and employee productivity appears to be lacking in the human resources management domain. Studies on work - life balance and employee productivity are few and most of them are limited to some specific geographical regions of the world and not even in the health sector. This has created a gap in the literature on work - life balance and employee productivity in 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. As such, the researcher intends to fill this gap.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted descriptive survey design because as a sample survey, the results would be generalized for the entire population of interest. Chibeze (2021) notes that studies of this nature use the survey method to look for information on facts, attitudes, practices and opinions of the respondents on the issues surrounding the subject matter of the investigation. To Obasi (1999), the use of survey is always adopted because it provides an important means of gathering information especially when the necessary data cannot be found in statistical records in form of secondary data.

Sources of Data

The data for the study came from two sources namely secondary and primary sources. Whereas the secondary came from academic journals and other published works in academics, the primary data were collected from the administration of the copies of the questionnaire to the respondents.

Area of the Study

The area covered by the study was 7-up Bottling Company Plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. It consists of five major departments as follows: Human Resources, Administrative, Maintenance, Marketing and Accounts.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of eight hundred employees of 7-up Bottling Company Plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.

Table 1: Population Distribution Table

Departments	Number
Human Resources	79
Administrative	105
Maintenance	295
Marketing	123
Accounts	196
Total	800

Source: Field Research, 2021

Sample Size Determination

In order to reduce the sample size to a manageable size, Taro Yamane's expression was used.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \text{Sample Size} \\ N &= \text{Total Population} \\ e &= \text{error margin, 5\%} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, substituting accordingly gives n as

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{800}{1 + 800(0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{800}{1 + 20} = \frac{800}{21} \\ &= 38.1 \end{aligned}$$

Sampling Technique

The stratified random sampling was utilized in this study. This was done by segmenting the employees based on their departments. This technique is appropriate in order to ensure that every element in the sampling frame has an equal opportunity of being selected (Orga, 2009).

Method of Data Collection

An item structured instrument of the five points modified Likert -Scale of strongly agree, agree, disagreed, strongly disagree and undecided, was developed by the researchers to collect data from the respondents on various issues surrounding work - life balance and employee performance of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. The data used for the study were substantially primary data and as such, they were collected through direct administration of the instrument to the respondents. The choice of this method was informed by the advantages it has over other methods. Firstly, it afforded the researchers the opportunity of assessing whether the respondents understood the questionnaire items. Secondly, it reduced the volume of non-response which often associates with surveys of this nature and thirdly, it made it possible for the researchers to make explanations or clarifications where necessary.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot study commissioned by the researcher. The process involved giving 20 copies of the instrument to 20 people selected out of the company being studied to complete. After an interval of two weeks, the same instrument was administered to the same group of people. Both the first and second responses were collated and analyzed through the application of Spearman rank order correlation coefficient. The exercise returned the following coefficients for the three research questions: 0.73, 0.90 and 0.80 respectively thus showing an average coefficient of 0.81 which implies that the instrument is 81 percent consistent and reliable.

Method of Data Analyses

Frequencies were used to give an indication of how many times a particular response occurred. And this assisted in fitting response into particular categories. Apart from being easy to interpret, percentages were also used to show comparisons between categories of response. In addition, the hypotheses formulated were tested using chi-square at 0.05 significant level.

Results

Data Presentation

Table 2: Response on the influence of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu

Response variable	Number Of Respondents	Percentage	of Respondents %
Strongly agree	157	58.8	
Agree	90	33.7	
Undecided	9	3.4	
Strongly disagree	6	2.2	
Disagree	5	1.9	
Total	267	100	

Source: **Field Survey, 2022**

From the table 2 a total of 157 respondents representing 58.8% strongly agreed, 90 respondents representing 33.7% agreed, 9 respondents representing 3.4% were undecided, 6 respondents representing 2.2% strongly disagreed while 5 respondents representing 1.9% disagreed.

Table 3: Response on the effect of telework on employee efficiency of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu

Response variable	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents %
Strongly agree	155	58.1
Agree	81	30.3
Undecided	15	5.6
Strongly disagree	9	3.4
Disagree	7	2.6
Total	267	100

Source: **Field Survey**, 2022

From the table 3, a total of 155 respondents representing 58.1% strongly agreed, 81 respondents representing 30.3% agreed, 15 respondents representing 5.6% were undecided, 9 respondents representing 3.4% strongly agreed while 7 respondents representing 2.6% disagreed.

Table 4: Response on the impact of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu

Response variable	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents %
Strongly agree	137	51.3
Agree	72	26.9
Undecided	28	10.5
Strongly disagree	20	7.5
Disagree	10	3.8
Total	267	100

Source: **Field Survey**, 2022

From the table 4, a total of 137 respondents representing 51.3% strongly agreed, 72 respondents representing 26.9% agreed, 28 respondents representing 10.5% were undecided, 20 respondents representing 7.5% strongly disagreed While 10 respondents representing 3.8% disagreed.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses generated in chapter one were tested using chi-square statistic. There was significant positive influence of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.

Table 5: Chi-square Calculation on influence of flexible time on employee output

Response	Fo	Fe	Fo-Fe	(Fo-Fe) ²	(Fo -Fe) ²	Fe
Strongly agree	157	53.4	103.6	10732.96	200.99	
Agree	90	53.4	36.6	1339.56	25.09	
Undecided	9	53.4	.44.4	1971.36	36.92	
Disagree	6	53.4	-47.4	2246.76	42.07	
Strongly disagree	5	53.4	-48.4	2342.56	43.87	
Total	267			348.94		

Table 5 showed that the calculated $\chi^2(348.94)$ is greater than the critical value of $\chi^2(11.34)$, we reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Therefore, there is significant positive impact of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.

Table 6 Chi-square Calculation on effect of telework on employee efficiency

Response	F _o	F _e	F _o -F _e	(F _o -F _e) ²	$\frac{(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e}$
Strongly agree	155	53.4	101.6	10322.56	193.31
Agree	81	53.4	27.6	761.76	14.27
Undecided	15	53.4	-38.4	1474.56	27.61
Disagree	9	53.4	-44.4	1971.36	36.92
Strongly disagree	7	53.4	-46.4	2152.96	40.32
Total	267				312.43

The table 6 showed that the calculated $\chi^2(312.43)$ is greater than the critical value of $\chi^2(11.34)$, we reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Therefore, there was significant positive effect of telework on employee efficiency of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.

Table 7 Chi-square Calculation on effect of shift work on employee effectiveness

Response	F _o	F _e	F _o -F _e	(F _o -F _e) ²	$\frac{(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e}$
Strongly agree	137	53.4	83.6	6988.96	130.88
Agree	72	53.4	18.6	345.96	6.48
Undecided	28	53.4	-25.4	645.16	12.08
Disagree	20	53.4	-33.4	1115.56	20.89
Strongly disagree	10	53.4	-43.4	1883.58	35.27
Total	267				205.6

The table 7 showed that the calculated $\chi^2(205.6)$ is greater than the critical value of $\chi^2(11.34)$, we reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Hence, there is significant positive effect of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis one indicated that there is significant positive impact of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. This is in accordance with Hon and Chon (2015), where he espoused the view that each of the work life balance policies on its own is a predictor of productivity. Hypothesis two revealed that there is significant positive effect of telework on employee efficiency of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. This is supported by Azeem and Akhtar (2014) where he stipulated that telework guarantees that employee in the health care sector have a moderate level of perceived work life balance, job satisfaction and commitment.

Hypothesis three indicated that there was the significant positive impact of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. This becomes clear since Akanji, Mordi, and Ojo (2015) maintained that there is a positive relationship between work-life balance practice and employee turnover.

Summary of Findings

- i. There was a significant positive influence of flexible time on employee output of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.
- ii. There was a significant positive effect of telework on employee efficiency of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.
- iii. There was a significant positive effect of shift work on employee effectiveness of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu.

Conclusion

The study investigated work-life balance and employee performance of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu. An employee is said to derive pleasure and self-fulfillment home and work when there is the lowest role conflict. Based on the review of literature, it is apparent that decision on issues relating to flextime, telecommuting, and job sharing form the basis for ensuring an efficient and employee attitude to work. A critical analysis of the subject matter of this research was carried out and discoveries have been made. Three variables which are flextime, job sharing and telework was used as a determinant of work-life balance for the study. The results revealed a moderate positive relationship between these identified factors on employee productivity. In addition, this contributed highly to creating a healthy, motivated workforce; enhance cooperation and individual productivity in the hospital. Therefore, based on the foregoing, this research concludes that of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu to achieve a high level of productivity, there is a need to pay more attention to the work-life balance of its workforce across all levels.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, it was therefore recommended that:

- i. Management of the 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu should focus more on different work-life balance incentives, such as (compressed work schedules, wellness programmes, and telecommuting) to enhance workers' productivity.
- ii. Management of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu should make provision for nursing mothers in terms of child care assistance which can be inform of crèche and after school services.
- iii. Management of 7-up Bottling Company plc. Ninth Mile Corner Enugu should ensure job sharing (shift work) for employees on essential duties to reduce the stress and also for them to have time for their respective families. By so doing, it will afford all employees the opportunity of total concentration on their work and also a better output.

Contribution to Knowledge

The study contributed to knowledge in the following ways:

The study provided valuable collection of ideas, facts, and figures that can be of importance to other researchers, entrepreneurs, lecturers, and students in comprehending the effects and relationships that exist between work-life balance and employee productivity. The empirical review of the relevant research on the effect of work-life balance on employee productivity showed that work-life balance is very significant to productivity. Most of these studies conducted in various nations around the globe all posited that work-life balance is essential in improving employee effectiveness and efficiency levels on the job. The study, therefore, provided a basis for research works and findings in these nations to be applied in business organisations alike in Nigeria. This contributes to knowledge by establishing that work-life balance facilitates productivity levels of workers. In previous studies, most researchers argue that work-life balance has a significant effect on the level of productivity of a worker. This study has therefore contributed to knowledge by pointing out that there is a significant relationship between work-life balance and employee productivity,

Suggestions for Further Studies

1. Work-life balance and employee productivity in Nigerian Banks.
2. Work-life balance and employee productivity in Nigerian petroleum sector.

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